

THROUGH AN INTERARTISTIC VIEW: PLASTICITY IN THE COLLECTIVE WORK CONSTELAÇÕES

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7295304

Rita Mychelly dos Santos Salles

Bachelor of Fine Arts and Master's in Arts at the Arts Center of the Federal University of Espírito Santo - UFES. Teacher of the Private Education Network of the State of Espírito Santo. Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/5099469795286805>. E-mail: ritamychelly@yahoo.com.br.

Ana Rita Cesar Lustosa

Graduated in Art and Master in Arts at the Arts Center of the Federal University of Espírito Santo - UFES. Teacher at the State Education Network of the State of Espírito Santo. Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/7290358656070206>. Email: lustosaanarita@gmail.com.

Dr. Sergio Rodrigues de Souza

Degree in Philosophy. Doctor in Pedagogical Sciences (UCPEJV - La Habana - CU). Post-Doctor in Psychology (UAJFK - Buenos Aires - AR). Email: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This article reflects on the inter-artistic perspective on plasticity in the collective Constelações, by Hilal Sami Hilal with the participation of young students from public schools from the state education of Vitória in ES, exhibited in 2016, in the cultural space of Palácio Anchieta - Headquarters of the State Government. To this end, the comparative image becomes the foundation of research, evidencing different points of view in relation to gestural, calligraphic and memory aspects in the creative process, approaching the relationship between matter and memory from the reflections of Henri Bergson. The interartistic studies of the work Constelações dialogue with aspects taken by subjective ideas, however, the metalinguistic character is intertwined with experiences and reconstructions through affective relationships, which are linked to the construction of identity, the evocation of personal or collective memory, which they translate and materialize in the expression of imagery. After some tests of the handmade paper recipe, improved techniques and poetic maturation, the experiments gave way to productions full of meanings, weaving plastic, aesthetic questions and philosophical reflections related to matter and memory. The manufacturing process took place in schools, crowded with affective memories. The main proposal of the Constellations project was to make possible artistic-pedagogical experiences

Keywords: Interartistic; plasticity; Hilal Sami Hilal; Time, matter and memory.

INTRODUCTION

Some artists from the *80's Generation*¹⁹ expanded their pictorial experimentation by appropriating varied raw materials, going beyond the traditional field, permeating conceptual ideas. In this sense, art often approaches a *philosophical act*. The field of philosophy is essential in the relationships and conceptions that broaden the subjectivities of plastic ideas. The concept of *the extended idea* permeates subjects that go beyond the pictorial plane of tradition.

Visual experiments using diversified raw materials have been used since the beginning of the 20th century in the field of arts. Aesthetic experiences intensified and proposed new relationships and conceptions in the subjective field of plastic ideas. However, from the 1980s onwards, the postmodern generation opened a range of new material essays that go beyond the traditional field of the arts, permeating between aesthetic, conceptual and philosophical ideas. The choice of material for the creation of the artistic object became loaded with symbolism.

For a better understanding and contextualization, this research seeks to weave comparative and interartistic reflections between the work *Seu Sami* with the structural anatomy of a brain “neural network”, that is, a network of neurons. Weaving a semiotic interrelation between the anatomically organic forms of both examples. This relationship between a work of art and a physical/anatomical form of something non-artistic will certainly not be an easy task, as we are used to working with comparative aesthetics or an intersemiotic translation from different comparisons and meanings; however, not so far away.

Faced with this scenario, the Brazilian artist Hilal Sami Hilal began his research and experimentation with handmade paper in the late 1970s. Hilal intensified his search for more knowledge about the manufacture of paper from organic fiber. He improved his techniques, in his travel experiences to Japan between 1981 and 1988, in search of knowledge about craft paper. Practice becomes the experimental basis for his artistic-poetic process. After some research and testing, the artist developed a new formulation of the recipe, starting in the 1990s with calligraphic tracery produced with handmade paper dough. (Figure 1)

¹⁹ **Geração 80** is an artistic trend in Brazilian art during the 1980s. In aesthetic terms, the main characteristic of the generation was the return to more subjective painting, given that, during the 1970s, movements such as conceptual art focused on mostly in *austere sculptural works*. The main milestone for this trend was the exhibition “How are you, Geração 80?”, held at the Escola de Artes Visuais do Parque Lage, in 1984, in which 123 artists from Brazil (especially from Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo) exhibited Your works.

Sources : Aoki, Virginia. *Connections with Art* . São Paulo: Moderna, 2013.

Figure 01: Hilal Sami Hilal, Renda, s/d.

Source : <http://galeriamariliarazuk.com.br/artistas/hilal-Sami-Hilal/biografia> . Accessed on 10/12/2019.

A descendant of a Syrian family, Hilal Sami Hilal was born in 1952 in Espírito Santo. In the 1970s, he began his degree in Fine Arts at the Federal University of Espírito Santo. Soon after, he began to dedicate himself to the academic area and taught for twenty years at the Department of Arts at the same university, where he founded the chair of Paper Studies. In addition to the *craft paper* discipline , he taught drawing, engraving, painting and others.

The artist moves through various media and languages to give shape to his concerns and plastic experimentation, raising questions among them the practice of appropriation of objects (clothes from family members as part of the recipe for handmade paper) in the poetic process. Thus, it is observed that this appropriation is impregnated with memory and maturation, loaded with the experience of a time that is transitory and reinvented as a support/painting. Thus, the relationships with the concept of the *expanded idea of art* become necessary to understand the process of articulation of the artist's thought and poetic action, seen in his productions with paper.

With the improvement of the art of papermaking, Hilal begins a process of maturation and poetic creation around handmade paper: a mixture of organic fiber, old clothes from family members, friends and a lot of affection, proposing dialogues mainly linked to the idea of memory. These symbolic aspects taken by subjective ideas, experiences and reconstructions through affective relationships are linked to the construction of identity, the evocation of personal and collective memory. These constructions of poetic thought run through his creative process and are symbolically present in the making of the mass of paper, which translate and

materialize in the imagery expressions. According to Ramaldes (2015, p. 70), “thinking about Hilal's poetry necessarily involves analyzing her creative process.”

For Herkenhoff, Hilal Sami Hilal uses paper as a “guiding thread for the making of these objects, so personal and delicate that they assume a permanent character in his works. Such incursions remain in the record of the experience [...]” (Herkenhoff, 2008, p. 92).

The production universe of the artist Hilal Sami Hilal merges in the relationship with materiality. The artist intensified his research with paper and thereby leveraged the possibilities of new meanings. According to Ramaldes (2015, p. 69), Hilal develops research with “materials testing their resistance, discovering new effects, inventing other ways of doing things and creating new languages to express themselves.”

In 2016, Hilal proposes a school project to the State Department of Education of Vitória (ES). It is an artistic and collective project that involved seven schools and more than 2500 students, who for two months made the entire plastic process exposed in the *Constellations exhibition*. The proposal for the exhibition was to promote the involvement of students, their affective, personal and collective memories, through art. The project was made possible with the support of schools, principals, teachers and the students themselves. The culmination was the production of more than 10 thousand names calligraphed with handmade paper dough, produced by the students themselves.

THE PROPOSAL

Hilal's poetic exploration is related from the raw material to the process of making and plastic creation. From the pasty base of paper, symbolic relationships arise due to the demand of the entire creative process. The artist's proposal was focused on the construction of the subject and its identity, through the experiences and experiences esplanade by the collective work itself.

Hilal proposed making craft paper with the students and working on calligraphy with the dough still wet. The central idea was to work signatures and names of people who were part of the student's affective bond. The artistic process was not simply geared towards craftsmanship itself, but was part of the entire procedural sequence of the activity, awakening in each student reflections on identity, memory and affection.

According to Ana Mae Barbosa (1998), the idea of teaching Art cannot be experienced with fixed rules and formulas, nor doing for the sake of doing, but developing a harmonious balance between knowing, doing and appreciating. Art must be assumed as a real expression of

being, being “possible to develop perception and imagination [...] to develop critical capacity, allowing to analyze the perceived reality and develop creativity in order to change the reality that was analyzed” (BARBOSA, 1998, p. 16).

In a playful way, the project was experienced with seven schools in the state network of Vitória. 10,000 calligraphed names were produced with the handmade paper dough. Each name carried its particularities, calligraphic originality. The manufacture of paper brings the idea of playfulness as pedagogical practices. Playfulness as a didactic teaching practice was intensely defended by the Brazilian philosopher and educator Paulo Freire, still in the 60's. Freire brought an innovative pedagogical methodology with practices that awakened in the student the relationship between human nature and the world, with teaching practices humanized and pedagogically playful.

With a humanized vision, teachers were able to better achieve their didactic goals, strengthening their respective praxis, which directly contributes to an autonomous formation of the student. Creating possibilities and accessible didactic strategy, provides gains in terms of creativity and the expression of intellect. Art shows itself as a strong ally in this process, contributing to the procedural formation of school life in a critical way.

For Hilal, in each name there is a memory, an experience and a life. Carrying out collective work would be a way to bring young people closer to art and contribute to their reflections and future perspectives (Neusa, 2016).

THE PROCESS

The artistic project, until its culmination with the *Constellations exhibition*, was experienced in two processes: teacher training and project execution with the support of students. The first stage began with the preparation of the directors and teachers of seven schools in the state education network in the municipality of Vitória. The training was developed “with the aim of bringing him closer to the experience with art, the “constellation”, the evocation of personal or collective memory, articulating the notion of identity” (Neusa, 2016, p. 33). With the support of the secretary of education, meetings were held so that the teachers could delve into the project, training it with theoretical preparation and workshops on the manufacture of handmade paper (Figure 2).

The teachers produced the paste based on crushed paper mixed with pigments. They developed a part of the original recipe and made adaptations for the school environment. The

project had the support of the pedagogical teams, which were prepared to conduct, together with the teachers, the entire productive and creative process of the students.

The experience in the second stage continued with the experiences developed over two months. Under the guidance of art educators and pedagogical support. The students literally got their hands dirty (Figure 2).

Figure 0 2: Hilal Sami Hilal and students in the process of creating the names with craft paper dough

Source: <https://maesmuseu.wixsite.com/maes/single-post/2016/08/04/pal%C3%A1cio-anchieta-o-universo-po%C3%A9tico-da-exposi%C3%A7%C3%A3o-constela%C3%A7%C3%B5es-de-hilal-sami-hilal>
Access: 11/18/21

The teachers involved were careful with the practices, providing the experiences during the project, which was not organized from top to bottom, but was developed from meetings and conversations that leveraged and provided the exchange of experiences and reflections among students. . Here, we highlight the importance of dialogue and approximation between the teacher and the student.

Based on this thought, Larrosa argues that,

Naming what we do, in education or elsewhere, as applied technique, as reflective praxis or as experience endowed with meaning, is not just a terminological issue. The words with which we name what we are, what we do, what we think, what we perceive or what we feel are more than just words (BONDÍA, 2002, p. 21).

Also according to Larrosa, words generate incentives and, as they are exposed, they carry many powers, as they are endowed with strength and “produce meaning, create realities and, at times, function as powerful mechanisms of subjectivation. [...] I believe that we do things with words and, also, that words do things with us” (BONDÍA, 2002, p 21).

A solid training, theoretical and empirical foundation, with a humanized vision, the teacher can better achieve their didactic goals, strengthening their respective praxis, which directly contributes to a more humane formation, proposing "possibility, let's say more existential (without being existentialist).) and more aesthetic (without being a beautician), namely, thinking about education based on experience/meaning" (BONDÍA, 2002, p.19).

This vision of the protagonist student allows the teacher to explore knowledge, transforming it into knowledge and experience that lead them to understand the artistic process as a spontaneous manifestation, strengthening personal and interpersonal ties.

After some tests of the handmade paper recipe, improved techniques and poetic maturation, the experimentations gave way to productions full of meanings, weaving plastic, aesthetic questions and philosophical reflections related to matter and memory . The manufacturing process took place in schools, crowded with affective memories. The main proposal of the *Constelações project* was to make artistic-pedagogical experiences possible.

The production of the paper pulp was experienced by students and teachers, for the making of names loaded with affection and reinvented as a support for the entire creative process - a process accompanied by dialogues, exchanges and experiences.

The paper dough recipe is pasty and resistant, and with the help of a confectioner's tube directly on the school table or plastic support, it became possible for students to calligraph their names and other names with affective relationships.

The plastic and aesthetic structure of the paper threads expressed from the tubes and created by the calligraphic gestures of the students allowed a visual experience compared to a web of names interconnected to each other – a constellation.

The confections of the names gained space, leaving the support position, giving them other meanings . Being like networks connected in firm lines, without knowing where the gestural dance of connections begins and ends, breaking barriers between the real and the symbolic, not only of plasticity, but of the subjectivity of the artist's poetic process.

On the side walls, blankets were installed with a composition of names glued one by one, connected and giving a continuous sequence. Textures, gradations, colors and tones provided opportunities for experiences and aroused symbolic assimilations of an interstellar medium . The calligraphic gestures appear loaded with proposals and subjectivities materialized in paper pulp. (Figure 3)

Figure 03: Collective exhibition Constellations. Hilal Sami Hilal. Anchieta Palace, ES

Source : < <https://maesmuseu.wixsite.com/maes/single-post/2016/08/04/pal%C3%A1cio-anchieta-o-universo-po%C3%A9tico-da-exposi%C3%A7%C3%A3o-constela%C3%A7%C3%B5es-de-hilal-sami-hilal>
>Access: 11/18/21

The installation *Constellations* fills a room in the exhibition space of Palácio Anchieta. The panels were composed of about 10 thousand names and each writing with its originality, memories, memory, identity, belonging and art. Fixed on light and translucent fabrics, the names intertwine between the support and the writing, a cluster of lines that interconnect in information and accumulations, causing a feeling of filling and gained amplitude with the installation of a large mirror on the ceiling, Hilal inserts the spectator himself as part of the constellation of names.

The installation suggests the idea of memory from the compositional plasticity of the exhibition and invites the viewer to the affective relationships that are permeated by a sense of belonging. It is a space for the projection of the imaginary, language and interpreting senses.

Such signatures, carried out on handmade paper applied on white organza covering the entire intention of the gallery wall, tend to reduce the size of the viewer in the face of their scale and mono-mentality. That single gesture evoked a great cloak. Handwriting becomes contagious, a field conducive to the multiplication of relationships that go beyond networks of signifiers, evoking concepts, bodies, gestures, images [...], Bringing with them affective memories flooded with memories and lived marks [...] (NEUSA, 2016, p. 27).

The work *Constellations* transcends material objectivity, permeated by subjective relationships. The idea of belonging that we work on in this interartistic study, refers beyond the anatomical-imagery aspects, crossings of a symbolic order. These connections are

imagetically related to family affective bonds, which, through the symbology of support, suggest a subjectivity in the senses converted into paper networks.

THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN MEMORY IN THE POETIC OUTCOMES OF THE *CONSTELLATIONS* INSTALLATION

The dialogues and connections related to the matter guide Hilal's experiments, and from the philosophical concepts of Henri Bergson, we brought reflections on *memory*, related to his creative process, evidencing a set of aesthetic, poetic, philosophical phenomena, composing dialogues with the interartistic ideas in his poetic process.

Hilal dialogues with symbolic aspects, especially those linked to the idea of memory. The *Constellations* exhibition talks about lived experiences, perhaps related to this past, present and future.

On the calligraphed blankets, the students deposited their experiences on different levels: their homesickness, remembrance, memories, which transcend the material character and objectivity of a translation.

time and *memory* as the essence of our existence acquires extraordinary importance. We are beings much more of memories than of the present; we have much more past than present and, therefore, what we remember is what actually constitutes us (Henri , 1991).

For Henri Bergson (1991), this consciousness would have similar actions and proportions in relation to the past and the future. The way memory acts in this process situates the present and the past, which are separated by a fine line. The Bergsonian thesis argues that “at all times we complete the present experience, enriching it with the acquired experience and, as this one does not cease to grow, it will end up receiving and submerging the other one” (BERGSON, 1991, p. 49).

CONCLUSION

Human existence and all its subjective elements are immersed in a world coded by man himself and all the experiences (good and bad) that cross him, creating, from his reminiscences, this particular and singular imagetic territory that is present. daily.

Spontaneous remembrance is something that not even time can erase, it is preserved in memory. Philosopher Henri Bergson called this process *memory-image*. We can thus say that the experiences, the wear and tear and the patches, the marks of temporality are images of a

memory that the artist sought with the proposal of the collective exhibition *Constelações*. Such memory-images arise as a process, due to a set of actions and constructions of a space impregnated by experiences, of rooted memories. In this sense, the use of materials, appropriation, intervention and combinations transform the creative process into a relationship of dialogues with time and memory.

interartistic studies of the work *Constelações* dialogue with the symbolic aspects taken by subjective ideas that intertwine with the personal experiences of both (artist-students and spectator) that translate and materialize their imagery.

REFERENCES

BARBOSA, Ana Mae. *Utopian Topics*. Belo Horizonte: C art, 1998.

BERGSON, Henri. *Matter and memory*. 2. Ed. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1991.

BONDÍA, Jorge L. (2002). Notes on the experience and the knowledge of experience. *Brazilian Journal of Education*. Rio de Janeiro, ANPEd, n. 19, p. 20-28, Apr. 2002 .

HERKENHOFF, P. *Seu Sami: Hilal Sami Hilal*. Sao Paulo, 2008.

MARIA APARECIDA, R. *Hilal's poetics Sami Hilal: Pages, books, calligraphic gestures and scriptures*. Vitória: EDUFES, 2015.

NEUSA, M. *Constellations: Hilal Sami Hilal*. Victory, 2016.